

A NEW TECHNIQUE FOR THE PREPARATION OF POLYETHYLENE FIBRE / POLYETHYLENE MATRIX COMPOSITES AND THE RESULTING MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

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SUMMARY: Different impregnation techniques for Polyethylene fibre / Polyethylene matrix composites using molten PE, PE powder and PE solution are described and discussed. Best results have been reached with the new solution impregnation method. The processing route includes an impregnation step in a saturated matrix solution. The growth of a matrix layer on the fibre surfaces in such a solution is shown by SEM micrographs. Further processing steps are the preparation of prepregs and their hot compacting to form PE/PE composites. In this work unidirectional composites were prepared at three compacting temperatures. The influence of the final processing temperature is discussed. Mechanical testing showed a high Young's modulus and a high tensile strength. The composite compressive strength is comparably low as a result of low compressive strength of the PE fibre.

KEYWORDS: polyethylene fibre, manufacturing, mechanical properties

INTRODUCTION

Ultra high modulus polyethylene (UHM PE) fibres exhibit high specific strength and stiffness combined with high strain to failure [1]. They especially improve the damage tolerance, fatigue and impact resistance and vibration damping when used as reinforcement for thermoplastic matrices. Polyethylene as matrix material is chemically resistant to most solvents, has a low coefficient of friction, is biocompatible and hydrophobe. Therefore it is widely used for biomedical application as in artificial hips or knee-joints [2]. A PE-fibre/PE-matrix composite would not only improve the mechanical properties of bulk PE but furthermore would enable to have a fully recyclable composite.

Impregnation of fibre bundles with matrix, this means the penetration of matrix into fibre bundles, the wetting of all fibres and the homogeneous distributions of the fibres in the matrix, is a very important step during composite manufacturing. Because many mechanical weak points of composites e.g. matrix rich areas or fibre contacts are founded in incomplete or imperfect impregnation. Using thermoplastic matrices the higher viscosity of the melt compared to uncured thermosetting plastics e.g. epoxy enlarged the difficulty in impregnation, because the higher viscosity leads to a reduced matrix flow.

Impregnation routes

HDPE and LDPE can potentially be used as matrix in a PE/PE-composite due to their lower melting temperatures than the UHM PE fibres [3-6]. However, the temperature window to produce the composite without damaging the fibres is rather narrow and the viscosity of the matrices in this temperature region are relatively high. Therefore impregnation of PE-fibre bundles with HDPE or LDPE matrices is rather difficult. Impregnation techniques can be classified by the condition of the matrices during the process. Figure 1 shows short results of impregnation experiments with HDPE and LDPE matrices.

	LDPE	HDPE
Melt	low penetration of matrix into bundle	
Powder	inhomogeneous powder distribution, agglomeration	
Solution	segregation and crystallisation of matrix on fibre surfaces	
	fibre volumen fraction: $V_f \geq 50\%$	$V_f \geq 85\%$

Figure 1: Results of the impregnation tests

For the melt impregnation tests UHM PE-fibre bundles (Dyneema, DSM The Netherlands) and HDPE-films are used. The fibre bundles were fixed in a mould to prevent shrinkage and stacked between HDPE-films. The mould was heated to 140°C for 15 minutes in laboratory press at a pressure of 4 bar. At the light micrograph (Fig. 2) of such a consolidated specimen, cut and polished perpendicular to fibre direction, three different areas can be seen. Outside of the bundle is the pure matrix (a). The outer part (b) of the bundle is impregnated. Fibre and matrix form a regular area, but in the middle of the bundle single fibres can be seen (c). Here, in this inner part of the bundle, isn't any matrix. The HDPE didn't flow into this inner part of the bundle caused by the high viscosity of molten matrix. Increasing the manufacturing temperature reduces the viscosity of matrix only a little, but just below melting point of fibre they melt at their surfaces, glue together and form a closed bundle. Therefore penetration of matrix into the bundle is stopped by a closed border of glued fibres. Increasing the impregnation time or using a LDPE with a lower melting point and a lower viscosity than HDPE didn't show a significant change of the Problem. However impregnation of PE / PE composites by melt impregnation technique is relatively difficult, caused by low penetration of matrix into fibre bundles (Fig. 1).

Figure 2: Melt impregnation, light micrograph of a polished crosssection

To impregnate fibre bundles with matrix powder, a very fine matrix powder is needed. The particle size of the powder should be in the range of the fibre diameter (10..25 μm). Dipping fibres in such a fine LDPE powder or shaking fibres in a box together with the powder resulted in a very inhomogeneous powder distribution with agglomerated LDPE particles (Fig. 1). Hinrichsen et al [6] published a work about continuous powder impregnation of UHM PE fibres with LDPE matrix. For impregnation they pulled the fibre bundles through a special fluidized bed chamber, heated them in a melting oven and compacted the tape between shaped rollers. For their paper they produced only a composite tape with a low fibre volume fraction of 10.8% and the problems of impregnation are increasing with increasing fibre volume fraction. However, this continuous powder impregnation technique is on the way to be a method to produce PE/PE composites.

Crystallisation of PE in a saturated solution is a well known fact. Dipping a high oriented substrate in such a solution, crystallisation is nucleated on the fibre surface [7]. An oriented layer around the fibres is growing. The novel idea of the present work is to use this phenomenon for producing PE/PE composites. Figure 3 shows UHM PE fibres after different times in a xylene solution with a low LDPE concentration (5 weight%) at 70°C. A thin layer of LDPE on surface of the treated fibres can be seen compare (Fig. 3a) untreated fibre and (Fig. 3b) 8 minutes treated fibres. The thickness of the layer increases with increasing treatment time (Fig 3b-d). After 19,5 hours the fibres are covered with a thick layer of LDPE (Fig. 3d).

Figure 3: Scanning electron micrographs of PE-fibres: (a) untreated, after treatment in LDPE/xylene for (b) 8 min, (c) 3,25 h and (d) 19,5 h.

The coated fibres turned out to be an ideal pre impregnated material, because each fibre is surrounded by the LDPE-matrix. Heating the parallel arranged impregnated fibres or fibre bundles and compacting them above the melting temperature of the matrix material leads to a one polymer composite with well defined fibre distribution. In contrast to our investigations with melt impregnated PE/PE composites, the high matrix viscosity (below the melting point of fibres) causes no problem, because the flow paths of matrix in the solution impregnated material are neglectible short.

In principal the solution impregnation method is working although with a HDPE matrix, but due to the less solubility of HDPE compared to LDPE it is more difficult to reach a thick matrix layer on fibre surfaces. Until now only thin HDPE layers, corresponding to 15 % matrix volume fraction have been achieved.

Composite fabrication

Figure 4 shows the discharge of the new manufacturing technique for PE/PE composites. It starts with commercial UHM PE fibres, Dyneema SK 65 (DSM, The Netherlands). In the first step, the solution impregnation, UHM PE fibre rowings (1760 dTex) were wound to bundles on a frame, dipped for 10 minutes in a 12 weight% solution of LDPE in xylene at 70°C and were dried in an oven at 50°C (experimental details are given elsewhere[8]). In figure 5a a thick regular coating of LDPE on fibre surface is visible. At higher magnification (Fig 5b) single coated fibres can be recognised. The fibre volume fraction was calculated by weighing the bundles before impregnation and after drying to 55%.

Figure 4: Discharge of the solution impregnation technique

Figure 5: Scanning electron micrographs of an impregnated PE-fibre bundle (a), (b) higher magnification

In the second manufacturing step several parallel arranged impregnated bundles were consolidated at 90°C in a laboratory press to get unidirectional prepregs. In the last step these prepregs were cut, laminated and pressed at 120°C, 130°C and 140°C for 10 minutes to unidirectional compression and tensile specimens. Alternatively NOL-Rings (diameter 100 mm) were wound with the impregnated bundles and heated at the same temperatures again for 10 minutes.

Mechanical Properties

Tensile modulus and strength were measured with flat specimen and NOL-rings. The tensile test results for different manufacturing temperatures are presented in Figure 6. The composites prepared at 120°C manufacturing temperature had a relatively high Young's modulus with values of 35 GPa, but the Young's modulus decreases with increasing manufacturing temperature. The Young's modulus of specimens consolidated at 140°C decreases to 20 GPa due to thermal damage of fibres which have a melting point of 146°C. Molecular and crystalline orientation decrease and the fibres shrink while treated at 140°C.

Figure 6: Tensile properties of LDPE / PE fibre composites

The tensile strength, measured with the NOL-ring specimen exceeded 1 GPa for all manufacturing temperatures (Fig. 6). An apparent maximum of strength can be observed at a manufacturing temperature of 130°C. It can be assumed that we have at this temperature a better fibre wetting and consolidation when compared to 120°C manufacturing temperature and of course no thermal damage when compared to 140°C manufacturing temperature. However, the tensile strength was nearly unaffected by the three consolidation temperatures. This was not expected, because the fibre strength is as the Young's modulus a function of fibre quality. We would expect the strength decrease also with increasing manufacturing temperature as it is the case for the Young's modulus. The rings and the flat specimens separately measuring the strength and the modulus respectively were manufactured by different techniques. The flat specimen were consolidated in a simple mould and the fibre shrinkage was only restricted by the viscosity of the melted matrix material and the consolidation pressure. The fibre shrinkage was macroscopically visible (e.g. about 10 % shrinkage at 140°C final consolidation temperature). To produce the ring specimens the

impregnated bundles were wound around a core. The ends were fixed in the mould during consolidation. Therefore fibre shrinkage was prevented and thermal damage of the fibres was lower compared to the flat specimens.

Figure 7 shows the fractured area of a NOL-ring failed in tension. The ring split into several parts (Fig. 7a). The SEM investigation shows that the bundles fibrillate into single polyethylene fibres (Fig. 7b). Figure 7c shows fibres with the for Dyneema typical not round crosssection. The fibres appear like a flat tape with axes of 10 to 25 μm (Fig. 7c). The fibres further fibrillate into macrofibrils with diameters of about 3 μm (Fig. 7d). The macrofibrils fibrillate into microfibrils with diameters of 0.5 μm (Fig. 7e). This shows that the failure mode is a hierarchically structured fibrillation with the hierarchies: microfibril, macrofibril, fibre, fibre bundle and specimen.

Figure 7: Light micrograph (a) and SEM micrograph (b-d) showing the different steps of fracture process

a) hole specimen, b) fibre bundle, c) single fibre,
d) macrofibril of fibre, e) microfibril of fibre

The results of the compression tests from the different manufacturing temperatures are summarised in Figure 8. The compression modulus showed the same decrease with increasing manufacturing temperature as the tensile modulus. Because of fibre misalignment the

Young's modulus in compression was lower as in tension. Tensile loading straightened the wavy fibres which led to a higher fibre alignment in the loading direction and an increased Young's modulus. In contrast, the fibre waviness in compression immediately leads to kinking and shear band format and thus a low Young's modulus. The low stiffness of the LDPE matrix accelerates this behaviour.

Figure 8: Compressive properties of LDPE / PE-fibre composites

The compressive strength of the PE/LDPE composites (Fig. 8) was just opposite to the high tensile strength (Fig. 6). The composite failed already at about 36 MPa. This low compressive strength was nearly unaffected by the manufacturing temperature. Figure 9 shows in a polarised light micrograph a specimen failed in compression. A kinkband through the whole specimen can be observed. This demonstrates the low compressive stability of UHM PE fibres in a LDPE matrix.

Figure 9: Polarized light micrograph of a specimen failed in compression

CONCLUSIONS

Different impregnation routes for PE/PE composites have been discussed. Melt impregnation techniques results in low penetration of matrix into bundle. Impregnation with PE powder leads to agglomeration and inhomogeneous distribution of powder particles. The new solution impregnation technique solves the impregnation problems. This manufacturing route starts with the impregnation of UHM PE fibre bundles in a LDPE / xylene solution. Further processing steps are preparation of prepregs and hot compacting to get the PE/PE composites. Mechanical testing shows a high Young's modulus and a high tensile strength. Because of their good tensile strength and further expected positive properties e.g. high energy absorption capacity, biocompatibility, and chemical resistance PE/PE composites are interesting for special applications, e.g. ballistic protection or as implant material for artificial joints.

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